

Bringing PBL to Education for Sustainable Development: University to Business (U2B) approach

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Abstract

Higher Education has to play a crucial and key driving part in providing Sustainable Development of society being a catalyst for it for the next generation. Its importance has significantly increased especially after adopting the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development by the United Nations; it is being recognized by increasing numbers of international community representatives. Higher Education plays a dual role in achieving all 17 Sustainable Development Goals. One aspect is integration of Sustainable Development issues in academic and research programs and projects. The other one is ability of Higher Education to promote them and empower their implementation in business and community. Higher Education has made a lot of progress in terms of embedding sustainable development at all levels in institutions, in sustainable development-based research, in curricula for sustainability, and boosting more collaboration between stakeholders in society. The aim of this paper is to share experience in applying Project-Based Learning in Sustainable Development curricula in Higher Education and identify the outcomes for different groups of stakeholders (teachers, students, businesses and society). This paper presents a case of National Research Mordovia State University in implementing University-to-Business approach (U2B) at the level of curricula that affect business community through engaging students in solving real problems in Sustainable Development. The study is based on content analysis of results of students' projects in Sustainable Development of enterprises and organizations, developing a maturity grid of organizational sustainability according to the Russian Federation Standard GOST R 54598.1 – 2015 "Management of sustainable development. Part 1. Guide". The results obtained show that providing good understanding of Sustainable Development for students Universities produce graduates that can take up leadership roles in taking decisions and translate the knowledge and skills to real-world applications.

Keywords: Higher Education; PBL; Sustainable development; University; Students; Business.

1 Introduction

Higher Education plays a dual role in achieving UN Sustainable Development Goals. On the one hand, it is reflected in integrating Sustainable Development issues in academic and research programs and projects. On the other hand, Higher Education promotes Sustainable Development philosophy and empowers its implementation in business and community boosting more collaboration between stakeholders in society.

One of the best ways to develop students' skills and solve real problems in Sustainable Development is Project-Based Learning. Project-Based Learning (PBL) is a widespread active learning strategy applied by Higher Education Institutions. According to assessment of the Active Learning Strategies Maturity levels Russian Universities are at the level of enlightenment in applying PBL – «while going through teaching and training learn more about the method benefits» (Mesquita et al, 2019).

The new Federal State Educational Standards of Higher Education in the Russian Federation that contain requirements for Bachelor's and Master's Degree programs include competences on development and implementation of projects. These universal competences are obligatory to students regardless of their majors within Bachelor's and Master's Degree programs. For instance, graduates of Bachelor's Degree programs should be «able to define tasks following the aims set and choose the optimal ways to solve them taking into account the law, resources and limitations» and graduates of Master's Degree programs should be «able to manage a project at all stages of its lifetime».

"Project-based learning is a student-centred instructional approach, in which learning is organized around projects. These projects involve complex, challenging and authentic tasks, on which students work relatively

autonomously (with a teacher playing the role of a facilitator) and over extended periods of time. The students collaborate in various design, problem-solving, decision making and investigative activities, the final goal being a realistic product or presentation" (Popescu, 2012).

Although there are many different views on PBL a list of its common characteristics can be identified:

- (1) Projects are central, not peripheral to the curriculum; students learn the main concepts of the curriculum via the project (Popescu, 2012).
- (2) It implies a problem or a question to organise and steer activities and the activities results in a final project that address the question (Lima et al, 2012).
- (3) It also entails involvement of student groups, or teams (Powell and Weenk, 2003).
- (4) PBL requires taking into account limitations of resources; particularly time (Yevstratova et al, 2018).
- (5) It is distinguished mostly by its interdisciplinary as projects are based on an open-ended problem and therefore they are not limited to one specific disciplinary area (Lima et al, 2012).
- (6) It does not only involve students in their own learning, as any other active methodology, it also involves teachers on improving their own practices (Alves et al, 2016).

And besides, PBL allows to implement a University-to-Business approach (U2B) at the level of curricula that affect business community through engaging students in solving real problems in Sustainable Development.

Universities play a pivotal role in providing high-level skills, a world-class research base and a culture of inquiry and innovation. The landscape of University-Business collaboration consists of a large number of highly diverse domains – for example, research projects, technology transfer, enterprise education, entrepreneurial support for staff and students, etc. (Wilson, 2012)

Findings of the project 'The State of University-Business Cooperation in Europe' in which over 17K representatives from within HEIs and business were involved show that more than half respondents of both HEIs and business initiate their cooperation and almost all of them plan to maintain or increase their cooperation. Both groups of the survey participants mention mutual commitment, mutual trust, shared goals, and prior relationships among relationships that facilitate University-Business cooperation (Davey et al, 2018).

Existence and expansion of good practice is to implement the U2B approach in degree programme design and delivery. Learning through projects enhances graduates' skills levels and ensures a smooth transition between university and business environments increasing opportunities for students to gain relevant work experience during their studies.

Taking in consideration these important remarks the paper provides a case of National Research Mordovia State University in implementing the U2B approach at the level of curricula that influences business through initiating students' projects to solve real problems in Sustainable Development. Therefore, the purpose of the paper is to share experience in applying Project-Based Learning in Sustainable Development curricula in Higher Education and identify the outcomes for different groups of stakeholders (teachers, students, businesses and society).

2 Methodology and Application of PBL to Education for Sustainable Development

The study is based on the content analysis of students' projects results in Sustainable Development for enterprises and organizations in 2016-2021 academic years, developing a maturity grid of organizational sustainability according to the National Standard GOST R 54598.1 – 2015 "Management of sustainable development. Part 1. Guide". It should be noted that the projects is a part of the course "Sustainable Development Management" studied by students enrolled in two Master's Degree programs: "Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Development" and "Integrated Management Systems" at National Research Mordovia State University. PBL in the course is based on a multi-level approach aiming at moving students from global and

national issues of Sustainable Development to organizational and individual levels. At the level of global issues the students study global initiatives in Sustainable Development, for instance UN Global Agenda 2030. At the national level, they investigate Sustainable Development strategies by countries focusing on strategic initiatives and national projects of the Russian Federation. At the organisational level students are supposed to study organization's sustainable development strategies, assessment of the maturity level of its sustainability, management solutions and best practices in promoting Sustainable Development values and achieving Sustainable Development goals (SDGs). At the individual level students develop projects "My contribution to sustainable development: past, present, future" to specify the SDGs that they consider to be priority and the most important for development of mankind's future and make a critical reflection about their contribution to achieve each of 17 SDGs (Salimova et al, 2020). The projects developed differ by their nature depending on the projects' aims and tasks (Table 1).

Table 1. Projects by their nature in the Management of Sustainable Development course.

Projects	by their nature		
	Research	University2Business	Student2Community
National strategies for sustainable development	√		
Organization's sustainable development strategies	√		
Assessment of the maturity level of the organization's sustainable development		√	
My contribution to sustainable development: past, present, future			√

The study presents a case of developing a U2B project "Assessment of the maturity level of the organization's Sustainable Development" as an example of applying PBL in promoting Sustainable Development philosophy. The aim of the project is to determine the level of organizational maturity in relation to the implementation of Sustainable Development principles. Students develop the project in the context of the organization being studied as a case of their Master's thesis. It assumes close cooperation with an organisation / enterprise team and provides a dual effect: enhancing students' skills levels and increasing their opportunities to gain relevant work experience during their study and engaging the enterprise in solving Sustainable Development problems (Table 2). The main stages of the projects carried out throughout the course are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 – Project Stages and Activities.

Phase	Classroom Activity	Activity in the Business setting
1	Identifying and setting aims and tasks of the project. Teacher's instructions on the final report, competence evaluation, and project evaluation	None
2	Review on methodology of evaluation of organizational sustainability maturity level (GOST R 54598.1 – 2015 "Management of sustainable development. Part 1. Guide")	None
3	Project follow-up meetings	Business visits and meetings. Teambuilding at the organization / enterprise
4	Mentoring by a teacher (on request)	Developing maturity grid for evaluation of organizational sustainability maturity level (case of enterprise)
5	Mentoring by a teacher (on request)	Assessment of the maturity level of the organization's sustainable development by the project team
6	Mentoring by a teacher (on request)	Developing a profile of organizational sustainability
7	Final presentation of the project and delivery of solutions. Competence and project evaluation	

At the first two stages a teacher describes a project concept including setting its aims and tasks, methodology that can be applied, timeline, resources needed and results, explains how the competences acquired and the project developed will be assessed. These stages are carried out in classroom. The third and fourth stages are preliminary steps to the project implementation. Follow-up meetings in the third stage are assumed by the teacher to clarify the progress in planning students' projects. At the same stage students start active communications with an organisation / enterprise. Students deliver aims and tasks of the project at the organisation / enterprise that is a case for their Master's theses and build a team incorporating the staff of the enterprise. Further stages are implemented on the site of the enterprise but teacher's mentoring is not excluded. At the fourth stage, the project team develop a maturity grid to evaluate an organizational sustainability maturity level on the methodology of the GOST R 54598.1 – 2015 "Management of sustainable development. Part 1. Guide". Key project activities are carried out at the fifth and sixth stages that include specifically assessment of the Sustainable Development maturity level of the organization and development of the organizational sustainability profile by the project team. At the final stage, students present their projects and deliver their solutions for the enterprises.

3 Results

The project "Assessment of the maturity level of the organization's Sustainable Development" is integrated in the Management of Sustainable Development course in two Master's programs – Integrated Management System and Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Development at National Research Mordovia State University since 2016. In 2016-2021 academic years over 100 students' projects have been developed for different industries (Table 3).

Table 3. Projects by Industry / Sector.

Projects by Industry / Sector	Years						Total
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	2	7	4		2	1	16
Manufacturing	4	4	8	12	4	5	37
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply		1	1	4	3	1	10
Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities				1			1
Construction		1	1	1			3
Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles		1	1		1		3
Transportation and storage					1		1
Information and communication		1	1	1	3		6
Financial and insurance activities		2	2	1	1		6
Professional, scientific and technical activities	1		1	1	2		5
Education	1	2	1	2	2	1	9
Human health and social work activities	1	1	1				3
Total	9	20	21	23	19	8	100

Low number of students' projects in 2021 can be explained by incompleteness of project activities in one out of two Master programs (students are at the fifth stage of the project at the time of preparing the paper for submission). The highest number of the projects – 1/3 of them for six years are carried out for industries that

are typical for the Mordovia region – Light engineering, Device engineering, Cable industry, etc. Almost 1/5 projects are developed for Agriculture and Forestry.

Methodology of the standard used implies applying a four-level scale to assess maturity of organizational sustainability from minimum to full maturity. Assessment criteria are practice of applying four principles of Sustainable Development: compliance with ethical standards, inclusion, responsible management, transparency. An excerpt of the students' project results is shown in Tables 4 and 5. The matrix for assessment of organizational sustainability maturity is developed by the same way for other three principles and practices respectively. The levels of maturity achieved by the company are marked in grey.

Table 4. Excerpt of matrix for assessment of organizational sustainability maturity (case of Forestry industry, Compliance with ethical standards principle).

Principles	Practice	Stages of achieving sustainable development by the organization			
		Minimum maturity		Full maturity	
Compliance with ethical standards	Traditions of sustainable development	Lack of knowledge and traditions in the sustainable development	Compliance with the main mandatory requirements of the Forest Code	The correlation of sustainable development with the benefits of business, its impact on society. Sustainable development is recognized as a critical element of professional practices, policies and procedures	Sustainable development is included at all levels of the organization, taking into account values and an ethical approach. Sustainable development is a part of strategic and operational planning and decision-making.
	Leadership	The leaders of the organization are not familiar with the principles and goals of sustainable development	Evidence of the organization's commitment to sustainable development, although it is not always consistent across all aspects of the organization (participation in the regional project "Forest conservation»)	Management's commitment to consistent sustainable development; published statements, policies, and sustainable development goals. Requirements of stakeholders in development and implementation of a sustainable development strategy are taken into account	Deployment of a sustainable development strategy in the organization. The organizational culture is based on the principles of SD. The organization implements them in its daily activities. Leaders by personal examples confirm their commitment to the principles and goals of sustainable development.

The materials presented in tables 4 and 5 and figure 1 are an excerpt of a student' project. Despite a general methodology used by students, each student project is unique since it is developed on the case of a single company taking into account management approaches and approaches to Sustainable Development used. Presentation of student projects' results allows to demonstrate a variety of approaches applied and compares the organisational maturity levels of Sustainable Development between organizations in the same industry.

Table 5. Assessment results of the maturity level of the organization's sustainable development by the project team (case of Forestry industry).

Principles of sustainable development	Practice of implementing SD principles	Average indicator by project team members	Average indicator of maturity level
Compliance with ethical standards	Traditions of sustainable development	1,75	1,88
	Leadership	2	
Inclusion	Identification of tasks and inclusion of stakeholders	1,75	1,75
	Creating an atmosphere of trust and opportunities for sustainable development	2	
Responsible management	Key management tasks, e.g. supply chain	1,75	2,25
	Assessment of environmental factors	3	
	Analysis	1,75	
Transparency	Sustainable Development Reporting and transparency to stakeholders	1,75	1,75
Overall maturity level			1,9

Summarized assessment results of the maturity level of the organization's sustainable development are presented in a spider graph (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Spider graph of the maturity level for a Forestry Industry case.

4 Conclusion

The results demonstrate that, Project Based Learning in the Management of Sustainable Development course as a case of the Higher Educational Institution provides outcomes for different groups of stakeholders (students, teachers, university, and business community).

Master's Degree students can master their competencies required by the educational standards and enhance methods of conducting research based on the business cases. Their close interaction with an organization and a project team provides good understanding of Sustainable Development philosophy and their engagement in solving real problems in this field. It helps them to take up leadership roles in taking decisions and translate the knowledge and skills to real-world applications. One of the benefits of the approach is also the possibility of embedding the results obtained by students in their research and master's thesis.

It also changes the role of teachers and involves them in improving their own practices. On the one hand, they provide mentoring support to students with theory and methodology; on the other hand, they closely collaborate with industry and identify its needs and open-end problems that give ideas for further joint academic and research projects.

Universities can greatly benefit from expanding the U2B approach and increase the level of involvement of students and graduates in research, the attractiveness of PBL, deploy the Sustainable Development philosophy in the educational process. They produce graduates that promote Sustainable Development values and methodology in business community.

The University-to-Business approach based on applying PBL in curricula allows to develop the maturity profile of the organization's sustainable development, identify its strengths and areas for improvement, collect data for possible adjustments to strategic approaches and management practices in Sustainable Development.

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